

Supplementary information

A.I Examples of manual determination of the center of the lesion for different ablation points and example of microelectrodes grouping for analysis.

We manually determined the center of the lesion as the region where the changes in the electrograms were maximal. Subsequently, we placed, always at the same distances from the center, the rings for the analysis. Finally, we assigned the microelectrodes that corresponded to each ring.

Figure I. Upper part) Examples of manual determination of the core of the lesion for three different ablation points at 1000 V. Lower part) Example of microelectrodes grouping for signal analysis. Once the lesion center was manually established, individual microelectrodes corresponding to the same ring were grouped. Three regions were used in the final analysis: center, border and periphery.

A. II Right Ventricle electrogram changes

Similar to the results provided in Figs. 3 and 4 of the main text, the same analysis is provided for the measurements performed in the right ventricle for 1000 V and 2000 V.

Figure II. Electrogram changes after PFA at 1000 V in the Right Ventricle. a) Example of electrogram morphology in the whole recording matrix at baseline and different time points after PFA application. Color circles represent the position of the rings that were subsequently analyzed (center, border and periphery). For illustrative purposes, in this figure and additional region (far) was included (black dashed line). b) Dynamic evolution of the mean values per region of the different parameters analyzed: ST-segment elevation (mV), RS amplitude (mV) and $|dV/dt|_{\max}$ (mV/s). Time=0 corresponds to baseline (pre-PFA); Time=1 min corresponds to post PFA. Values are reported as mean and SD (vertical lines).

Figure III. Electrogram changes after PFA at 2000 V in the Right Ventricle. a) Example of electrogram morphology in the whole recording matrix at baseline and different time points after PFA application. Color circles represent the position of the rings that were subsequently analyzed (center, border and periphery). b) Dynamic evolution of the mean values per region of the different parameters analyzed: ST-segment elevation (mV), RS amplitude (mV) and $|dV/dt|_{max}$ (mV/s). Time=0 corresponds to baseline (pre-PFA); Time=1 min corresponds to post PFA. Values are reported as mean and SD (vertical lines).

A. III Temperature measurements

In order to accurately measure, the temperature rise during PFA application, a temperature fiber optic sensor based on GaAs (gallium arsenide) technology was used (bare tip sensor THR-NS-1165C, FISO Technologies, INC, Canada). The optic fiber sensor (diameter 243 μm) was carefully fixed at the border of the metallic tip electrode right on the cardiac tissue/electrode interface (see Figure III). Temperature was acquired at a sampling rate of 125 Hz.

The measurements in Fig. III show the mean temperature recorded for different application points at 1000 and 2000 V. After each PFA application (a biphasic burst of 100 μs), temperature sharply increases and subsequently decreases with slower dynamics between consecutive bursts. As shown, there is a clear non-linear dependence on voltage; at 1000 V the maximum temperature variation was around 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ while for 2000 V, temperature considerably increased with a maximum variation up to 15 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. These results show how during focal PFA, non-negligible thermal values can be reached. However, it must be noted that although for 2000 V the maximum temperature momentarily reached 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, it was demonstrated that this temperature level, maintained for a very short duration (<2 seconds) will not cause permanent thermal damage ²⁹. Moreover, the temperature values displayed were recorded around the point of maximum heating because at the border of the electrode tip, the electric field intensity is maximum. Finally, it is important to consider that the PFA applications were performed epicardially in an open chest approach and no irrigation was used. In endocardial applications, the blood cooling effect should reduce the maximum temperature measured.

Figure IV. Temperature recordings during PFA. Upper figure displays a schematic of the catheter tip and the position of the temperature probe during measurements. In the lower part of the figure, temperature recordings are displayed for 1000 V (red) and 2000 V (blue). Values are reported as mean (solid line) \pm SD (show areas) (n=5).

A. IV Zoomed view of the temporal changes of the local electrograms

Fig. V depicts the array of electrodes and a zoomed view of the temporal changes in a selected electrogram at baseline and 10 and 60 minutes after the PFA applications. In order to clarify how the different parameters were calculated, the figure also shows color markers over the signal (to visually quantify the changes in ST and RS amplitudes) and a magnification of the electrograms depicting the calculation of the dV/dt_{max} as the maxim slope of the EGM signal.

Figure V. Zoomed view of the temporal changes in a selected local electrogram at baseline and 10 and 60 minutes after the PFA applications. The upper row of the figure shows a representation of the electrode matrix and rectangle identifying the selected electrode, at baseline, 10 and 60 min post PFA application. The central part shows the zoomed view of the selected electrogram at baseline, 10 and 60 min post PFA application. Each electrogram has 4 markers identifying how the ST (red markers) and RS amplitudes (yellow markers) were calculated. The bottom row shows a magnification of the electrograms indicating the maximum slope, which corresponds to the $|(dV/dt)|_{max}$ value.

Supplementary Table I

Table I displays the values of the different parameters recorded at baseline, at the end of the 60 min recording period and for a subset of points at 180 min after PFA application.

		1000 V			2000V			
		Baseline	60 min	180 min (n=2)	Baseline	60 min	180 min (n=2)	
ST- segment elevation (mV)	Lesion center	0.0±0.3	0.5±0.2	0,1±0,0	Lesion center	0.0±0.3	0.8±0.6	0,2±0,1
	Lesion border	0.0±0.2	0.3±0.2	0,2±0,0	Lesion border	0.1±0.2	0.4±0.4	0,1±0,1
	Lesion periphery	0.0±0.1	0.2±0.2	0,3±0,1	Lesion periphery	0.1±0.3	0.3±0.3	0,0±0,1
RS amplitude (mv)	Lesion center	6.0±3.3	2.6±0.7	2,3±0,4	Lesion center	6.7±1.9	3.4±1.5	3,5±0,2
	Lesion border	5.5±2.8	2.9±0.9	2,6±0,0	Lesion border	5.5±2.3	3.9±1.4	3,6±0,5
	Lesion periphery	5.7±2.8	3.1±0.9	3,3±0,6	Lesion periphery	5.4±2.8	4.3±0.9	3,5±0,4
$ (dV/dt) _{\max}$ (mv/s)	Lesion center	2938±2216	843±333	513±30	Lesion center	2962±1864	713±321	628±118
	Lesion border	2666±2354	822±321	856±267	Lesion border	2644±2085	938±384	793±29
	Lesion periphery	3413±2360	1329±825	1627±1077	Lesion periphery	2208±1885	1029±613	891±222

Video Legends

Video V1. Dynamic representation of the evolution of electrograms in all the electrodes contained in the recording matrix after PFA at 1000 V. Although the system continuously acquired data during 60 min post PFA, in the video only one measurement per minute has been included for simplicity.

Video V2. Dynamic representation of the evolution of electrograms in all the electrodes contained in the recording matrix after PFA at 2000 V. Although the system continuously acquired data during 60 min post PFA, in the video only one measurement per minute has been included for simplicity.